

FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN STUDENTS OF SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract:

The article examines the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students of secondary educational institutions, pedagogical observations from research and the results of questionnaires.

Key words: *health, depression, physical culture, training, energy, proper nutrition.*

Introduction

Relevance of the research work: Many stadiums, reservoirs, sports complexes and palaces are being built within the framework of five important initiatives to educate our youth as physically healthy and spiritually mature people, says President Shavkat Mirziyoev, – The most important thing is that among our children, who regularly engage in sports and make a healthy lifestyle their life goal. the number of boys and girls is expanding.

Promoting a healthy lifestyle among students of higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the current problems in the field of education. Decree No. PF-6099 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2020 "On measures for the wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports" was issued. In the presidential decree, the main directions of wide implementation of "Healthy lifestyle" and further development of mass sports were determined. According to the decree of the President, families, classes on creating conditions for physical education and mass sports and developing mass sports in every family, neighborhood and district (city), in pre-school, general secondary, special secondary, professional and higher educational institutions and other organizations, instructions and practical recommendations were given on regular sports competitions between cocktail teams and regions. In the development of "Healthy lifestyle" among students of secondary education institutions, first of all, students' acquisition of theoretical and practical knowledge on health and hygiene is of great importance.

METHODOLOGY: The promotion of a healthy lifestyle is adequately covered in training manuals, textbooks and other literature. In a healthy lifestyle, we should consider health first. Health is covered in many literatures as follows:

Health is not only the absence of disease or physical defects, but also a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being. Health should be strengthened first of all, that is, it is necessary to give methodical instructions on how to prevent stress in students of higher education institutions. A student may need to learn self-control and engage in other activities to overcome depression.

As for the concept of a healthy lifestyle, a healthy lifestyle is defined as active actions aimed at improving and protecting human health. Sh.Kh., one of the leading scientists of the field of "Physical culture" of the Republic of Uzbekistan on healthy lifestyle. Honkeldiev and others published a textbook entitled "Physical Culture of a Healthy Lifestyle". The textbook contains useful information for young people involved in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, that is, students of general secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges, and students of higher educational institutions. In the textbook "Physical culture of a healthy lifestyle", the daily movement activities of students are clearly indicated within the framework of regulation. That is, it is assumed that each student can make his own agenda. Having a daily schedule is a great help in developing the internal and external conditions of each student's body.

A healthy diet plays a big role in planning the daily routine, a healthy diet is considered to be a diet that ensures a person's life activity, normal growth and development, strengthens his health and helps prevent diseases. In a healthy lifestyle, healthy eating is not about eating a large amount of food at once, it is necessary to take into account the nutritional value of the food. It is assumed that the content of the food contains sufficient minerals, proteins, and fats. Each substance affects the student's development negatively or positively. The consumption of large amounts of fats and carbohydrates leads to excess weight gain. It is assumed that the content of the food contains sufficient minerals, proteins, and fats. Each substance affects the student's development negatively or positively. The consumption of large amounts of fats and carbohydrates leads to excess weight gain.

Eating 3 or 4 meals during the day is included in the standard content. If the student's health is impaired, it is necessary to eat 6 or 7 meals less and more frequently in order to restore the internal reserves of the body. It is also necessary to eat food at the right time. It is recommended to chew each bite at least 15-20 times. Eating in this order will not cause any gastrointestinal diseases.

In the life of society, health is the first and most important need of a person, it determines his ability to work and ensures the full development of a person. This is the most important condition for knowing the surrounding world, self-affirmation and human happiness. A healthy lifestyle is a life based on the principles of moral, active, hard work, and patience, and at the same time, it protects against the negative effects of the environment, and allows to maintain moral, mental and physical health until old age. Moral health is the basis of human social life determined by moral principles. Signs of a person's moral health are, first of all, a conscious attitude to work, mastering cultural treasures, and actively abandoning habits and customs that are contrary to the normal way of life. A healthy lifestyle is a necessary condition for the development of various aspects of human life, an active long life and the full performance of social functions.

According to Y. P. Lisitsyn, human health largely depends on lifestyle and sleep. Currently, the most complete definitions of this concept can be distinguished in the scientific system of knowledge about a person, and the following definitions are given in relation to a healthy lifestyle:

- healthy lifestyle - a system of views on health problems that develop during life under the influence of various factors as a clear expression of a person's ability to achieve any goal he sets;
- a healthy way of life - a way of organizing production, domestic and cultural aspects of life, which is formed in a person and allows to realize one's creative potential to one or another level;
- healthy lifestyle - a socially and historically determined idea of health care, as well as means and methods of integrating it into practical life;
- a healthy lifestyle - typical forms of daily human activity, which strengthen and improve the reserve capabilities of the organism, thereby ensuring the successful performance of social and professional functions, regardless of gender, economic and socio-psychological status.

The relevance of a healthy lifestyle is related to the increase and change of stresses on the human body as a result of the increasing complexity of social life, man-made, ecological, psychological, political and military threats that cause negative changes. The main tasks that should be implemented in Uzbekistan on the basis of the development strategy are the establishment of a people-friendly state by increasing human dignity and further developing a free civil society; making the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country, ensuring rapid development of the national economy and high growth rates; conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital, ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level, approaching universal problems based on national interests; strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open pragmatic and active foreign policy, and above all, developing a healthy lifestyle for the citizens of Uzbekistan. In modernizing Uzbekistan, human health, physical fitness, and having a culture of a healthy lifestyle are extremely important social values. Ensuring the health of the nation and preserving the national gene pool can be solved in a sufficiently positive way only thanks to a healthy lifestyle. These are all social institutions of the society; family, educational institutions, neighborhood, and independent education, the issue of conveying the meaning and essence of a healthy lifestyle to the citizens of our society, raising young people to be alert, knowledgeable, well-rounded individuals. A healthy lifestyle— consists of the process of formation of a person who works actively, approaches work on the basis of creativity, easily eliminates strong physical and mental pressures, extremely dangerous and harmful factors, and develops in all aspects. The thinking and health of citizens living in Uzbekistan depend on their property and moral values. Also leads to positive results in his views. In modernizing Uzbekistan, the formation of a healthy lifestyle is carried out on the basis of the formation of the worldview of citizens based on worldly knowledge, moral and spiritual education based on religious values. The ideology of a healthy lifestyle, according to R.U.Arzikulov, is life

It should incorporate the philosophy of lifestyle, the state's policy on the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the legal and ethical foundations of a healthy lifestyle, pedagogy, psychology, sociological culture, ethics and aesthetics of a healthy lifestyle. A healthy lifestyle regulates and accelerates the process of forming healthy relationships and exemplary behavior between people in the process of renewal in Uzbekistan. The motivation factor is also important in the formation of a healthy lifestyle, and motivation means that a person starts to perform a certain activity, moves it, justifies and explains its importance.

RESULTS. A survey was conducted on the development of a healthy lifestyle among 25 students of the Samarkand Medical Technical University.

Questionnaires of the survey about the correct adherence of students to a healthy lifestyle:

How long do you sleep during the day?

Do you exercise during the day?

Do you know the nutritional value of the food you eat?

What do you mean by a healthy lifestyle?

Do you find that following a routine has a positive or negative effect on your health?

Have you received any healthy lifestyle advice from family members?

Do you think that the proverb "healthy body-healthy mind" is true?

According to the results of the survey, all 25 students answered yes to the 1st question and said they will follow the agenda. To question 2, 31 students answered that they sleep 6-8 hours, 14 students answered that they sleep 4-5 hours. According to question 3, 25 students answered that they do physical education during the day. "Do you know the nutritional value of the food you eat?" 25 students answered yes to question 4.

15 students answered the rules of hygiene and 12 students answered about the need to pay attention to nutrition to the 5th question asking what do you understand by the term "healthy lifestyle". answered that it shows that your weight is normal. Do you think that following a healthy lifestyle develops strength, speed, agility, endurance, and flexibility from physical qualities? All students answered yes to 8 questions. Have you received any healthy lifestyle advice from family members? 15 students answered yes and 10 students answered yes to the question.

CONCLUSION. instead, we can say that in order to develop a healthy lifestyle among the students of the Samarkand Medical Technical University, as well as the students of higher education institutions, it is necessary to organize special seminars, webinars and trainings for them during the month. By following a healthy lifestyle, we will be able to clearly observe that students' mental, mental, and physical activities have developed to a certain extent. We hope that it will prevent widespread diseases among students.

The issue of raising a healthy generation in Uzbekistan is one of the most important issues in state policy. In the foreign policy of Uzbekistan, the main attention is paid to the issue of mutual equality and beneficial cooperation, while in the domestic policy, the issue of ensuring a happy and prosperous life of citizens and their healthy lifestyle is gaining urgent importance. Have a healthy lifestyle

Harmonization of religious and secular values in its development determines the future development path of Uzbekistan based on the harmony of national and universal values.

According to R. Matibayeva, the most important condition in raising children is that the family is built on a strong, morally healthy foundation. So, healthy children in a healthy family, our country worthy children, that is, they will grow up to be a mature generation that thinks creatively, makes independent conclusions, and can make a worthy contribution to the prospect of Uzbekistan's independence, regardless of what field of expertise they will be in the future.

LITERATURE:

1. Mallayeva Mavjudaxon Maxramovna - Toksik Hepatit Sharoitida Qonning Ayrim Biokimyoviy (Alt, Ast, Ishqoriy Fosfotaza Va Umumiy Oqsil Miqdori) O'Zgarishlariga Polifenollar Ta'sirini Aniqlash.
2. Маллаева М. Б. ЭКОЛОГИЯ ҲИСОБИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ //SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 4. – С. 269-280.
3. Маллаева М. М. СОГЛОМ ТУРМУШ ТАРЗИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 16. – С. 753-760.

4. Маллаева М. М. СОГЛОМ ТУРМУШ ТАРЗИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШИ //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 16. – С. 753-760.
5. Muhammadjon M., Mavjudaxon M. EKSPERIMENTAL TOKSIK GEPATITDA AYRIM POLIFENOLLARNING TA'SIRI //International Journal Of Contemporary Scientific And Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 283-286.
6. Maxramovna M. M. Et Al. PEDAGOGICAL ESSENCE OF DEVELOPING A CULTURE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE //Web Of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 1234-1238.
7. Mallaeva Mavjudakhan Mahramovna, Khidirov Nemat Chorshanbievich, Kiyomov Ikhtiyor Ergashovich - GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) ISSN (E): 2347-6915, Vol. 11, Issue 2, Feb. (2023)
8. Рахимова Д. Д., Шайхова Г. И. 7-17 YOSHLI MAKTAB OQUVCHILARINING JISMONIY RIVOJLANISHINI VAHOLASH //ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРОНЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 4.
9. Рахимова Д.Ж. Самарқанд вилоятида болалар ва ўсмирлар ўртасида витаминлар, макро-ва микроэлементлар етишмовчилигининг клиник белгилари бўйича тарқалишини таҳлил қилиш. Problems of biology and medicine том 140. №6. Ст-161.https://scholar.google.com/citations?viewop=view_citation&hl=ru&user=8WW94nYAAAAJ&citation_for_view=8WW94nYAAAAJ:_FxGoFyzp5QC
10. Raximova D. J., Naimova Z. S., Halimova S. A. 7 yoshdan 14 yoshgacha bo 'lgan bolalarda oziqlanish muammolari va ularni oldini olishda vitamin va minerallarning o 'rni //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 380-385. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/7-yoshdan-14-yoshgacha-bo-lgan-bolalarda-oziqlanish-muammolari-va-ularni-oldini-olishda-vitamin-va-minerallarning-o-rni/viewer>
11. Рахимова Д. Ж. и др. ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПНЕВМОНИИ КОРОНАВИРУСНОЙ ЭТИОЛОГИИ (COVID-19) КОМБИНАЦИЕЙ ПУЛЬС ТЕРАПИИ С
12. ИММУНОДЕПРЕССАНТАМИ //Re-health journal. – 2020. – №. 4 (8). – С. 59-64.
13. M.A.Mustafakulov, M.M.Mallayeva. Eksperimetal Toksik Gepatitda Ayrim Polifenollarning Ta'siri - Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar – 283
14. Mallayeva Mavjudaxon Maxramovna, Uz - Elektron Hisoblash Mashinalari Uchun Yaratilgan Dasturning Rasmiy Ro'yxatdan O'tkazilganligi To'g'risidagi Guvohnoma - DGU 30291
15. Маллаева Мавжудахон Махрамовна.- “Каламуш Жигар Антиоксидант Тизимиغا Полифеноллар Экстрактини Таъсири”. – Программа Научно Практической Конференции С Международным Участием
16. Маллаева Мавжуда Махрамовна - Современные Методы Исследования Показателей Микроклимата Комнат. "Применение Высоких Инновационных Технологий В Профилактической Медицине"
17. Jurakulovna R. D. Analysis of Distribution of Vitamins, Macro and Micro Elements Deficiency among Children and Adolescents in Samarkand Region, According To Clinical Symptoms //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 229-235.
18. Islamovna S. G., Jurakulovna R. D., Gulistan K. Current state of the problem of rationalization of schoolchildren's nutrition. – 2022.

19. Jurakulovna R. D. et al. EFFECTIVENESS OF STREPTOKINASE AND PROPOFOL DRUGS IN PATIENTS WITH CORONAVIRUS DELTA STRAW (EXAMPLES FROM PRACTICE). – 2021.
20. Raximova D. J., Naimova Z. S., Halimova S. A. 7 yoshdan 14 yoshgacha bo‘lgan bolalarda oziqlanish muammolari va ularni oldini olishda vitamin va minerallarning o‘rni //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 380-385.
21. Zhurakulovna R. D., Abdurakhmanovna U. N. Current State of the Problem of Rationalization of Schoolchildren's Nutrition //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. 2023. – T. 19. – C. 81-89.
22. Zhurakulovna R. D. Nutrition of children as a factor determining the health of future 287-291
23. Zhurakulovna R. D., Shomuratovna B. R., Narmuminovna G. G. HYGIENIC RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE PREVENTION OF SCHOOL MYOPIA AND OTHER VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS IN CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – T. 6. – C. 29-38.
24. Zhurakulovna R. D. ASSESSMENT OF THE ACTUAL NUTRITION OF CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT REGIONAL PECULIARITIES //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – C. 41-44.